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FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF EUDRAGIT COATED PECTIN SODIUM ALGINATE BEADS OF TRAMADOL HYDROCHLORIDE FOR COLON TARGETING

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ABSTRACT

The main goal of present work is to design a colon specific drug delivery of Tramadol hydrochloride multiparticulate systems by using sodium alginate and pectin polymers. Beads are coated with eudragit polymer for achieving colon specific by combining both pH and polymer based drug delivery. Pectin sodium alginate beads were prepared by ionotropic gelation method by using calcium chloride as cross linking agent. Coating is carried out by oil in oil solvent evaporation method. Particle size analysis, entrapment efficiency, scanning electron microscopy studies, swelling studies and *In vitro* dissolution studies were carried out. The optimized formulation was used for determining the analgesic activity by using eddy's hot plate technique and tail flicking method. The % drug release was highest for the formulation TCB1 i.e. 93.2% and the controlled release was shown by the formulation TCB9 i.e. 74%. Biological evaluation was carried out and the percentage increase in reaction time was found to be 81.3% for the eddy's hot plate method and the tail flicking latency time was found to be 93.13% for the optimized formulation (TCB9). It suggests that the optimized formulation showed increased resistance than the standard. The studies had clearly indicated that Tramadol hydrochloride through the pectin sodium alginate beads were very effective to deliver the drug specifically to colon.

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INTRODUCTION

Colonic drug delivery is intended for the local treatment of gastrointestinal disorders like ulcerative colitis, irritable bowel syndrome and can potentially be used for colon cancer or the systemic administration of drugs that are adversely affected by the upper gastro-intestinal (GI) tract. The advantages of local treatment in the colon have been described: reduced incidence of systemic side effects, administration of lower doses of drug, and maintenance of the drug in its intact form as close as possible to the target site. Precise colon drug delivery requires that the triggering mechanism in the delivery system only respond to the physiological conditions particular to the colon¹. Natural polysaccharides are now extensively used for the development of solid dosage forms for delivery of drug to the colon (i.e. pectin, chitosan, cyclodextrin, and dextran). The rationale for the development of a polysaccharide based delivery system for colon is the ability of the colonic microflora to degrade various types of polysaccharides that escape small bowel digestion². Pectins are polysaccharides components of plant cell walls and consist of linear polymers of d-galacturonic acid residues with varying degrees of methyl ester substituents³. The degree of esterification (DE) and degree of amidation (DA), which are both expressed as a percentage of carboxyl groups (esterified or amidated), are important means to classify pectins. Pectins are broken down by various microbial sources including human colonic bacteria and may therefore be utilized as colonic delivery systems if their solubility is reduced⁴.

Single-unit dosage forms for colonic delivery may suffer from the disadvantage of unwarranted disintegration of the formulation due to high inter- and intra-subject variability and poor reproducibility, which may lead to loss of local therapeutic action in the colon. Therefore little emphasis is being laid on the preparation of multi-particulate delivery systems in comparison to single-unit dosage forms due to their possible benefits, like better bioavailability, decreased risk of local irritation and predictable gastric emptying.⁵ The multiparticulate systems may spread out on their arrival in the colon, with a sharp increase of surface area exposed to bacterial breakdown that produces a rapid drug release and thereby improves drug availability and gives site-specific action to the colon. Tramadol HCl is a centrally-acting analgesic, used in treating moderate to moderately severe pain and for the treatment of functional gastrointestinal disorders such as irritable bowel syndrome. The most common functional GI disorders are irritable bowel syndrome and non-cardiac chest pain. It is estimated 15-20% of the general population are affected by IBS. It has been reported that the most commonly occurring adverse side effects during treatment of pain with tramadol preparations are gastrointestinal upsets. Between one third and a half of patients suffer nausea and vomiting initially when started on tramadol pain therapy. Patients with IBS exhibit increased gut sensitivity, suggesting that at least part of the problem may be because the nerves that carry information from the gut to the brain, the afferent neurons, produce a response greater than that expected to be produced by the stimuli they have received, which results in non painful stimuli being perceived as painful (visceral hyperalgesia)^{6,7}. Targeting of Tramadol hydrochloride to the colon may provide adequate treatment for IBS and allow a reduction in dosage and possible systemic side effects. Successful targeted delivery of drugs to the colon via the gastrointestinal tract requires the protection of a drug from degradation, release and absorption in stomach and small intestine and then ensures abrupt or controlled release in the proximal colon. This might be achieved by the use of specially designed drug delivery system that can protect the drug during its transfer to colon^{8,9}. In this work, a multiparticulate system of Tramadol hydrochloride for the treatment of irritable bowel syndrome was developed by utilizing the pH-dependent solubility of eudragit polymers and microbial degradability of Pectin polymers. Drug loaded Pectin beads were prepared, and then coated with eudragit polymer. This polymer shows the solubility at or above pH 7.

MATERIALS

Materials used included Tramadol Hydrochloride was kindly provided as a gift sample by MMC health care Limited (Chennai, India). Pectin was purchased from Loba chemicals, Mumbai and Sodium alginate from Burgoyne urbidges & co. Calcium chloride from Merck, Mumbai.

METHODS

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The DSC thermograms were recorded on a DSC (model DSC-60, Shimadzu). Samples were heated in hermetically sealed aluminum pans over temperature range of 10⁰C – 300⁰C at a constant rate of 10⁰C/min under nitrogen purge.

Fourier Transform Infra Red Spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR spectra were obtained on FTIR-8400S (Shimadzu). Samples were prepared in KBr disks. Data were collected over a spectral region from 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The surface characteristics of samples were studied by scanning electron microscopy using quanta 200 scanning electron microscope. Micrographs with different magnifications were recorded to study the morphological and surface characteristics of the solid dispersions.

Formulation

The pectin sodium alginate beads were prepared by ionotropic gelation technique. First, required amount of pectin was dispersed in a specified volume of distilled water containing the drug and allowed to swell for 2 hours. In another beaker suitable amount of sodium alginate was taken and mixed well with 10 ml of water. The pectin solution containing the drug was added to sodium alginate solution with stirring for 15-20 minutes to produce a viscous form. Then polymer drug solution was added drop wise by using syringe having needle of 26 G into a beaker containing different concentrations of solution of calcium chloride from a specific height. So the gelatinous precipitate is formed by chemical reaction between sodium alginate and calcium chloride. The prepared beads then removed by filtration and washed with distilled water and dried and stored in well closed container for further use.^{10, 11}

Coating procedure^{12, 13}

Pectin sodium alginate beads were coated with eudragit using oil-in-oil solvent evaporation method. Pectin sodium alginate beads (50 mg) were dispersed in 10 mL of coating solution prepared by dissolving 500 mg of Eudragit L and S in 1:2 ratio in ethanol : acetone (2:1) to give 5:1 (coat :core ratio). This organic phase was then poured in 70 mL of light liquid paraffin containing 1% wt/vol Span 80. The system was maintained under agitation speed of 1000 rpm at room temperature for 3 hours to allow for the evaporation of solvent. Finally, the coated beads were filtered, washed with n-hexane, and dried overnight.

CHARACTERIZATION OF PECTIN SODIUM ALGINATE BEADS**Yield of pectin sodium alginate beads**

The yield of the beads was expressed as percentage of the weight of the dried beads at room temperature compared to the theoretical amount. Percent yield is to be calculated by using the Equation:1

$$\text{Percent yield} = \frac{\text{The amount of beads obtained (g)}}{\text{Theoretical amount (g)}} \times 100 \text{ (Equation 1)}$$

Size analysis of pectin sodium alginate beads

The mean diameter of 100 dried beads was determined by optical microscopy (Metzer, India). The optical microscope was fitted with a stage micrometer by which the size of beads could be determined.

Flow Properties¹⁴**Bulk density (D_b)**

The bulk density of the formulated beads was evaluated using a bulk density apparatus. It is the ratio of total mass to the bulk volume of beads. It was measured by pouring the weighed pectin sodium alginate beads into a graduated measuring cylinder and the volume was noted. It is expressed in gm/cc and is given by

$D_b = M/V_b$ (Equation 2)

Where, M - Mass of the powder

V_b - Bulk volume of the powder.

Tapped density (D_t)

It is the ratio of total mass to the tapped volume of the beads. The tapped volume was measured by tapping the beads to constant volume. It is expressed in gram/ml and is given by

 $D_t = M/V_t$ (Equation 3)

Where, M - Mass of the powder

V_t - Tapped volume of the powder.

Compressibility index (I) and Hausner's ratio

Carr's index and Hausner's ratio measure the propensity of beads to be compressed and the flow ability of beads. Carr's index and Hausner's ratio were calculated using following formula.

 $C.I = (D_t - D_b) 100/D_t$ (Equation 4)

Where, D_t - Tapped density of the powder

D_b - Bulk density of the powder

Hausner's ratio **$Hausner's\ ratio = D_t/D_b = V_b/V_t$ (Equation 5)**

Where, D_t - Tapped density of the powder

D_b - Bulk density of the powder

Angle of repose

The frictional forces in a loose powder can be measured by the angle of repose. This is the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of beads and the horizontal plane. Sufficient quantities of beads were passed through a funnel from a particular height (2 cm) onto a flat surface until it formed a heap, which touched the tip of the funnel. The height and radius of the heap were measured. The angle of repose was calculated using the formula.

Angle of repose $\theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$ (Equation 6)

Where, h - Height of the pile

r - Radius of the pile

Entrapment efficiency

50 mg of drug loaded pectin sodium alginate beads were dispersed in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 at $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and kept for digestion up to 24 h. Then the sample was centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 10 min to remove any insoluble solids, the supernatant layer was removed and filtered. The drug content was determined using UV

visible spectrophotometric method at 279 nm. Entrapment efficiency was calculated using the following formula

Table: 1 Formulation of Tramadol loaded colon targeting sodium alginate pectin beads

Formulation code	Concentration of pectin (% w/v)	Concentration of Na alginate (% w/v)	Concentration of Ca chloride (% w/v)
TCB1	1	2	5
TCB2	2	2	5
TCB3	3	2	5
TCB4	1	2	10
TCB5	2	2	10
TCB6	3	2	10
TCB7	1	2	15
TCB8	2	2	15
TCB9	3	2	15

Table: 2 Particle size distribution of Tramadol hydrochloride loaded colon targeting beads

S. No	Formulation	Mean diameter (μm)
1	TCB1	752
2	TCB2	837
3	TCB3	954
4	TCB4	638
5	TCB5	784
6	TCB6	859
7	TCB7	485
8	TCB8	523
9	TCB9	748

Table: 3 Flow properties Tramadol hydrochloride loaded colon targeting sodium alginate pectin beads

S.NO	Formulation	Angle of repose	Carr's index	Hausner's ratio
1	TCB1	22.14 ± 0.86	13.5 ± 0.10	1.15 ± 0.03
2	TCB2	22.49 ± 1.18	18.06 ± 0.41	1.18 ± 0.01
3	TCB3	22.59 ± 0.72	18.13 ± 0.50	1.22 ± 0.04
4	TCB4	22.02 ± 0.68	18.2 ± 0.52	1.13 ± 0.01
5	TCB5	24.77 ± 0.39	19.26 ± 0.41	1.23 ± 0.03
6	TCB6	24.90 ± 0.68	19.53 ± 0.23	1.25 ± 0.04
7	TCB7	27.03 ± 0.80	19.33 ± 0.11	1.24 ± 0.02
8	TCB8	27.36 ± 0.26	13.86 ± 0.25	1.11 ± 0.07
9	TCB9	26.69 ± 0.40	13.25 ± 0.41	1.13 ± 0.01

% Entrapment = (Actual content / Theoretical content) x 100 (Equation 7)

Swelling studies

The beads were weighed (50mg) and suspended in petriplates containing phosphate buffer of pH 6.8. The petriplates were then placed aside. The beads were separated at every time point up to 6 hr, blotted with filter paper to remove the excess water, and weighed.

Swelling ratio SR = $W_g - W_0 / W_0$ (Equation 8)

Where, SR indicates swelling ratio;

W_0 , initial weight of beads

W_g , final weight of beads

Invitro dissolution studies^{15, 16}

The *Invitro* dissolution test was done in USP basket apparatus with a stirring speed of 50 rpm at 37°C in 900 ml dissolution medium. The simulation of the gastric pH and transit time were achieved by altering the pH of the dissolution medium at different time intervals. The pH of the dissolution medium was kept 1.2 for 2 hrs using 0.1 N HCl. After 2 hrs 1.7 g of KH₂PO₄ and 2.225 g of Na₂PO₄.2H₂O were added the pH of the dissolution medium was adjusted to pH 7.4 by adding 1.0 M NaOH and the dissolution was carried out for 3 hrs. After 5 hrs the pH of the dissolution medium was adjusted to 6.8 with 0.1 N HCl and maintained upto 12 hrs. For every 1 hr the samples were withdrawn from the dissolution medium and replaced with the fresh medium of corresponding pH. The samples were analyzed by using UV- visible spectrometrically at λ_{max} of 278nm.

Stability Studies

The stability studies were performed as per ICH guidelines at temperature of 40° C / 75% RH (Long term stability study) for 3 months. The optimized formulation was analyzed for drug content and % drug release.¹⁷

Biological evaluation

Table: 4 % Entrapment efficiency of Tramadol hydrochloride loaded colon targeting sodium alginate pectin beads

Formulation	% Entrapment efficiency
TCB1	45.23
TCB2	52.72
TCB3	63.96
TCB4	54.63
TCB5	63.98
TCB6	71.39
TCB7	58.27
TCB8	67.21
TCB9	77.36

Table: 5 Data showing swelling behaviour of the Tramadol hydrochloride loaded colon targeting sodium alginate pectin beads

Time (hr)	Formulations								
	TCB1	TCB2	TCB3	TCB4	TCB5	TCB6	TCB7	TCB8	TCB9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	14	16	26	12	16	12	2	6	4
2	30	34	74	26	34	28	18	22	18
3	56	58	117	54	46	56	26	50	32
4	88	76	150	68	78	64	36	58	46
5	118	90	178	94	88	76	46	62	68
6	148	124	186	112	114	92	58	70	84

Procurement and housing of animals

Albino rats of wistar strain (200-250 g) of either sex were procured from the central animal house of the institute. They were housed in standard polypropylene cages and kept under controlled room temperature ($24 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$; relative humidity 60-70%) in a 12 hr light dark cycle. The rats were given a standard laboratory diet and water ad libitum. Food was withdrawn 12 hr before and during the experiment. Protocols were approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee, registered under CPCSEA.

Eddy's hot plate method

The male rat were weighed and divided into three different groups (n = 6 in each group). Group I served as control. Group II (Tramadol hydrochloride 5mg/kg body weight) served as standard and groups III was treated with the optimized formulation. The reaction time of animals was noted down on hot plate after 3 hrs after the

treatment. The basal reaction was time taken by observing hind paw licking or jump response (whichever appear first) in animals while placed on hot plate, which was maintained at constant temperature 55⁰C. A cut off period of 10 seconds was observed to avoid damage to the paws. The percentage increase or decrease in reaction time (as index of analgesia) at each time interval was calculated.¹⁸

$$\text{Percentage increase in reaction time} = \frac{R_t}{R_c} - 1 \times 100 \text{ (Equation 9)}$$

Where R_t is reaction time in treated group

R_c is reaction time in control group

Tail flicking method

After one hour of drug administration, the tip of tail was dipped up to 5 cm into hot water maintained at 50-55⁰C. The response time was noted down after 3 hr as the sudden withdrawal of the tail from the hot water¹⁹. Cut off time of 10 seconds was maintained to avoid damage to the tail for all groups. The time required for flicking of the tail, was recorded.

$$\% \text{ inhibition of pain} = \frac{V_{\text{control}} - V_{\text{treated}}}{V_{\text{control}}} \times 100 \text{ (Equation 10)}$$

Where V_{controlled}= mean tail flick in controlled group

V_{treated} = mean time of tail flick in test and standard group

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

From DSC thermograms the melting point of pure drug Tramadol hydrochloride was found to be 187⁰ C, which is close to the value reported in literature hence the procured drug is pure form. The physical mixture DSC thermograms indicate that there are no interactions between the drugs and excipients which can be accessed from the peaks in the DSC thermograms.

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) study

FTIR results have been depicted in figure no.2. An IR spectrum of pure Tramadol Hydrochloride showed the peaks 3306 cm⁻¹ (Hydrogen bonding), 2929 cm⁻¹ (C-H stretching of OCH₃), 2604 cm⁻¹ (-C-H stretching of -CH₂ and CH₃ groups), 1606 cm⁻¹ (C=C ring stretching), 1288 cm⁻¹ (-C-H bending of symmetric and asymmetric of -CH₂ and CH₃). These peaks can be considered as characteristic peaks of Tramadol Hydrochloride and were not affected with polymers and prominently observed in IR spectra of Tramadol Hydrochloride along with polymers as shown in the figure 2. This indicated that there was no interaction between Tramadol Hydrochloride and polymers sodium alginate and pectin.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscopy images at magnifications 30 and 100 are shown in figure3. TCB3, TCB7, TCB9 of the prepared beads were evaluated for the surface morphology and shown in the Fig. no.3. Scanning electron microscopy revealed that the prepared beads were spherical and the surface of the beads was rough. The scanning electron microscopy results showed that the spherical nature of the beads increases as the concentration of calcium chloride increases.

Figure: 1 Differential scanning calorimetry thermograms of Tramadol hydrochloride, sodium alginate, pectin and physical mixture.

Figure: 2 FT-IR spectroscopy. Spectra of Tramadol hydrochloride, sodium alginate, pectin and physical mixture.

Figure: 3 Scanning electron micrographs of Tramadol loaded colon targeting pectin sodium alginate beads at (a) Magnification 100. (b) Magnification 30.

Particle size analysis

Particle size analysis values were tabulated in table 2. By increasing the calcium chloride concentration, the degree of cross linking in the particles increases which inturn reduces the size of the beads.

Flow properties

The prepared formulations of Tramadol hydrochloride showed θ values in 22-27°. Carr's index values ranges from 13.25- 19.53 and the hausner's ratio value from 1.11-1.25. The values of flow properties were shown in the table 3. The angle of repose (θ) is a characteristic of the internal friction or cohesion of the particles, the value of the angle of repose will be high if the powder is cohesive and low if the powder is non-cohesive. The prepared formulations of Tramadol hydrochloride showed θ values in 22-27° with acceptable flowability according to the angle of repose measurements. Carr's index up to 21 is considered of acceptable flow property. Hausner's ratio was related to the inter particle friction, the powders with low interparticle friction, had ratios of approximately 1.25 indicating good flow. The prepared formulations showed good to excellent flow properties.

Entrapment efficiency

The entrapment efficiency is highest for the formulation TCB3 and it is lowest for the formulation TCB7 that are 77.26% and 45.23% respectively. The values are given in table 4. Beads obtained from a 15% counter-ion solution had a higher percentage of encapsulation because the quantity of matrix (pectinate and alginate) in these beads were larger than for 5% and 10% of counter ion. This might be due to the presence of two types of protective layers in beads, one of calcium pectinate and other one is calcium alginate, which prevented the diffusion of drug more effectively than a single type of layer only and the higher cross linking capacity of 15% of calcium chloride also prevents the diffusion of drug. As the proportion of pectin was reduced in the combination of these two polymers, the drug content of beads started to reduce. It can be explained that as the concentration of calcium pectinate increases more effective prevention of diffusion of drug occurs. Therefore increased calcium pectinate layer was responsible for the maximum drug content.

Figure: 4 Particle size distribution of pectin sodium alginate beads of Tramadol Hydrochloride Flow properties

Figure: 5 Plot showing swelling studies of pectin sodium alginate beads of Tramadol Hydrochloride

Figure: 6 *In vitro* release profiles of pectin sodium alginate beads of Tramadol hydrochloride at pH 1.2, 7.4 and 6.8

Figure: 7 Percentage drug release of optimized formulation subjected for stability testing

Figure: 8 Plot of increase in reaction time for the optimized formulation

Figure: 9 Plot of increase in tail flicking latency time for the optimized formulation

Table: 6: *In vitro* release profile of Tramadol hydrochloride loaded colon targeting pectin sodium alginate beads at pH 1.2, 7.4 and 6.8

Time (Hr)	Cumulative % drug release								
	TCB1	TCB2	TCB3	TCB4	TCB5	TCB6	TCB7	TCB8	TCB9
1	1.0±0.08	1.17±0.8	2.6±0.8	7.2±0.7	1.1±0.7	2.5±0.8	0.8±0.1	0.9±0.1	7.3±1.6
2	8.7±1.3	10.1±2.4	4.4±1.3	9.3±0.5	1.3±0.6	3.6±0.7	7.0±1.1	10.0±1.1	7.5±1.0
3	15.6±1.9	17.0±2.7	8.9±0.7	14.1±3.8	14.2±0.9	8.7±0.7	14.4±0.9	13.4±2.0	14.7±5.2
4	26.0±1.5	25.4±0.5	15.4±1.2	21.4±3.4	17.4±0.4	16.9±1.1	22.5±1.0	24.1±1.6	23.4±0.2
5	31.3±0.7	28.6±0.9	19.6±0.4	29.7±5.5	18.8±0.9	20.7±2.0	27.6±0.9	29.0±0.5	26.6±0.9
6	52.4±1.6	51.1±1.0	34.9±4.2	55.7±3.0	46.1±0.6	31.6±2.2	44.8±1.0	50.2±0.7	46.0±1.0
7	61.0±0.6	58.3±0.5	40.3±3.5	62.4±4.1	50.7±0.5	36.1±2.1	53.9±1.2	59.5±1.1	48.6±0.9
8	67.4±1.1	68.0±1.0	46.4±3.1	69.5±5.9	53.3±1.1	42.2±1.1	61.1±0.7	63.2±0.9	53.3±0.8
9	73.9±1.7	77.4±0.8	55.8±1.4	74.7±5.4	61.7±0.4	55.4±3.5	70.9±1.2	69.5±1.5	58.4±0.5
10	82.2±1.1	81.7±0.7	64.1±3.1	81.7±3.4	67.6±1.1	64.6±2.4	75.6±0.8	75.9±2.7	64.0±0.7
11	87.5±1.5	86.7±1.0	72.7±2.9	85.3±3.9	79.1±0.7	72.5±1.5	77.8±1.9	79.3±0.9	68.5±1.8
12	93.2±1.5	91.9±1.0	77.1±3.0	89.8±2.4	86.1±1.2	76.5±1.6	87.5±1.6	82.3±1.3	74.0±0.9

Table: 7 Correlation coefficient (r^2) values for the fit of different kinetic models

Formulation code	Zero order	First order	Higuchi model	Korsmeyer peppas model	Hixon crowell cube th root model
TCB1	0.982	0.931	0.888	0.950	0.965
TCB2	0.980	0.930	0.884	0.949	0.967
TCB3	0.978	0.923	0.839	0.984	0.949
TCB4	0.958	0.946	0.873	0.950	0.966
TCB5	0.968	0.902	0.843	0.927	0.941
TCB6	0.975	0.908	0.829	0.980	0.936
TCB7	0.983	0.936	0.879	0.953	0.971
TCB8	0.970	0.968	0.888	0.935	0.976
TCB9	0.981	0.973	0.903	0.963	0.980

Swelling studies

The % swelling is highest for the formulation TCB3 and it is lowest for the formulation TCB7 that are 186% and 58% respectively. The percentage swelling values are tabulated in table 5. By increasing the calcium chloride concentration, the degree of cross linking in the particles increases which reduces the amount of water that can

Table: 8 Percentage drug content of optimized formulation subjected for stability testing

Formulation code	Before stability study	After stability study		
		1 month	2 month	3 month
TCM9	31.98	31.73	31.45	31.37

penetrate into the particle. The higher degrees of cross linking produced particles with denser structures that reduce the permeability of the particle giving the decreasing trend in particle swellability. The formulation containing 15 % of calcium chloride has high degree of cross linking since this will prevent colonic fluids rapidly swelling the pectin particle.

Invitro dissolution studies

The cumulative % drug release was highest for the formulation TCB1 i.e. 93.2% and the controlled release was shown by the formulation TCB9 i.e. 74% and the values are shown in the table 6.

The drug release pattern was affected by ratio of polymer mixture and the % of calcium chloride. The results indicate that the drug release slows down with increasing polymer concentration. It can be explained that greater the amount of polymer, thicker the layer of polymer was formed around the drug particles and more effectively the polymer would hold the drug with itself. This might be due to the presence of barrier layers of calcium pectinate and calcium alginate in the beads, which caused the slow release of drug from beads. Increasing calcium concentration led to a greater degree of cross-linking and aggregation of the polymer chains inducing higher gel strength and limiting swelling patterns and subsequent drug release from the beads.

Release kinetics

The drug release profiles from the Tramadol hydrochloride loaded sodium alinate pectin beads were fitted to various kinetic models such as zero order, first order, Higuchi, Peppas, Hixson-Crowell cubeth root model. The values of correlation coefficient (r^2) are calculated and given in Table 7. The correlation coefficient of TCB1, TCB2, TCB5, TCB7 and TCB9 is high for Zero order model suggesting that they follow zero order release kinetics which indicates that the optimized formulation follows controlled release.

Stability studies

The stability study is performed for the optimized formulation and the % drug content values are tabulated in table 8 and the % cumulative drug release values were shown in the figure 7. In view of the potential utility of optimized formulation for targeting of Tramadol hydrochloride to colon, stability studies were carried out at 40°C / 75% RH for 3 months to assess their long term stability. There is no appreciable change in drug content and dissolution profile of optimized formulation after storage at 40°C / 75% RH for 3 months.

Biological evaluation

The percentage increase in reaction time was found to be 81.3% for the optimized formulation. The percentage increase in tail flicking latency time was found to be 93.13% for the optimized formulation. The data showed that the colon targeting pectin sodium alginate beads have release of Tramadol hydrochloride over a long period

of time. The colon targeting beads are significantly more effective than the standard drug in both tail flicking and eddy's hot plate method.

CONCLUSION

The designed site-specific delivery of from the system may reduce the side effects of the drug caused by its absorption from the upper part of the GI tract when given in conventional dosage forms such as tablets and capsules. The increase in the counter-ion solution grew up the strength of the pectinate and alginate gel involving two mechanisms: intermolecular cross-linking following the "egg-box" model and non-ionic hydrogen bonding or hydrophobic interactions. Increasing concentration of the counter-ion led to a greater degree of cross-linking of pectin chains inducing stronger gel and reducing swelling and drug release. The experimental results demonstrated that Eudragit coated pectin sodium alginate beads have the potential to be used as a drug carrier for an effective colon-targeted delivery system.

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